

ENERGY AND EXERGY-BASED SIZING OPTIMIZATION OF A STAND-ALONE HYBRID RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The combination of solar and hydrogen energy has been recently proposed as a sustainable approach in hybrid renewable energy systems. This study proposes an energy system which integrates solar photovoltaic and solar thermal energy along with hydrogen energy storage to supply heating, cooling and domestic hot water demands of a stand-alone building in Tehran. A dynamic modeling is carried out by the TRNSYS software and particle swarm optimization is utilized to size the system such that minimum loss of power supply probability, exergy destruction and dumped electrical power are achieved. The optimized configuration delivers 30.54 MWh of energy, leaving no loss in power supply and no electricity dump. The exergy analysis reveals that 73% of the total exergy destruction is caused by the photovoltaic array followed by the solar thermal collector, alkaline electrolyzer and proton exchange membrane fuel cell. The PV array's size is also found to have a direct linear impact on the total exergy destruction, making it the least efficient component and primary driver of exergy loss. Meanwhile, the electrolyzer power is found to be exponentially related to the amount of electricity dump.

Keywords: *Hybrid Renewable Energy System (HRES), Hydrogen Energy Storage, Exergy, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Stand-alone, TRNSYS*

INTRODUCTION

HVAC systems account for approximately 40-50% of a building's total energy consumption, making them the most energy-intensive building services [1–3]. Relying on fossil-based power grids to supply the necessary electricity for these systems can lead to significant environmental harm and place additional strain on the grid. By using Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HRES), which typically integrate multiple renewable energy sources and energy storage techniques, it is possible to sustainably provide energy and reduce reliance on power grid [4,5]. Batteries and Hydrogen Energy Storage (HES) methods have been broadly proposed in the literature as backup power sources for Photovoltaic (PV)-powered systems, ensuring minimum Loss of Power Supply Probability (LPSP) [6–8]. In this case, the surplus electrical energy produced by the PV system is stored by either the battery or the water electrolysis process for later use. Given the intermittent nature of solar energy, it is crucial to accurately size the HRES to optimize both performance and costs.

Numerous sizing methods and optimization approaches have been suggested, with the majority focusing on techno-economic indicators such as LPSP, Net Present Cost (NPC), and Levelized Cost Of Energy (LCOE) as objective functions [9]. Haffaf et al. [10] suggested that almost 98% of the studies considered economic parameters. Other criteria such as environmental factors and exergetic performance have been less frequently analyzed. Nevertheless, as highlighted by Dincer et al. [11], having an exergetically sound performance is also of primary importance in sustainable energy systems.

Recently, meta-heuristic optimization techniques have been utilized in energy management of HRESs equipped with HES and they have been reported to provide highly accurate results [12]. Among these techniques, Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) have been widely employed. These two methods were used by Kamal et al. [13] in their study to minimize NPC and the cost of energy for a self-sufficient rural power supply system in India. For the same application in Egypt, multi-objective PSO was implemented to maximize Renewable Energy Fraction (REF) and minimize LSPS as well as cost of energy [14]. PSO along with Cultural Algorithm (CA) and Jaya Algorithm was employed by Tazay et al. [15] to obtain the optimal NPC of an HRES incorporating solar and wind energy as well as hydrogen fuel cell and battery bank with maximum LPSP of 2%. In this study, PSO was found to have the fastest response. Izadi et al. [16] assessed the performance of a similar system in

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various regions of Iran and utilized GA to obtain minimal emission, and capital expenditure by optimizing the number of PV units and wind turbines. In an innovative study by Siddiqui and Dincer [17], a GA-based optimization approach was used to achieve the lowest cost rate and highest exergy efficiency in a trigeneration system that utilizes wind and solar energy to produce electricity, hydrogen, and ammonia.

As the literature review shows, techno-economic performance of HRESs has been extensively discussed but other aspects such as energetic and exergetic analysis have been mostly overlooked. The present study analyzes a stand-alone solar powered HRES integrating PV modules, solar thermal collectors and hydrogen fuel cell to fully meet the energy demand for air conditioning and Domestic Hot Water (DHW). PSO is proposed to find an optimal sizing which leads to the least exergy destruction and electrical energy dump.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The case study building is a single-story 180-m² residential unit, located in Tehran. An HRES combining solar PV and solar thermal energy with hydrogen energy storage is proposed to meet its heating, cooling and DHW energy demands throughout the year. Heating and cooling demands are supplied by an air conditioning unit equipped with a vapor compression heat pump with COP of 4.5. Meanwhile, DHW is provided by a solar thermal collector equipped with a hot water storage tank. The annual heating, cooling and DHW loads are approximately 14.35, 12.30 and 3.89 MWh respectively.

The schematic representation of the proposed HRES is illustrated in Figure 1. As shown, the electrical power generated by the PV array is utilized to meet the power consumed by the heat pump. The surplus electrical energy is directed to an alkaline electrolyzer to produce hydrogen gas. This hydrogen is subsequently stored in a storage tank for later utilization in a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cell, thereby ensuring a continuous energy supply during periods of low or absent solar energy input. Similarly, the solar thermal energy obtained by a flat plate collector is stored in a storage tank.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the proposed system

EXERGY ANALYSIS

Exergy input to the system is primarily received by the PV and collector arrays. The exergy input rate for these units can be calculated using Equation 1 and 2, [18–20] :

$$\dot{E}x_{in,PV} = G \times A_{PV} \times n \left[1 - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{T_{am}}{T_{so}} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{T_{am}}{T_{so}} \right)^4 \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{in,Col} = \left(1 - \frac{T_{am}}{T_{so}} \right) \dot{Q}_{so} \quad (2)$$

In this study, T_{so} represents the apparent surface temperature of the sun as the exergy source, which is assumed to be 5777 K. \dot{Q}_{so} is the heat absorption rate in the solar collector and can be obtained from:

$$\dot{Q}_{so} = G(\tau\alpha) A_{Col} \quad (3)$$

Exergy destruction mainly occurs within the PV array, the solar collector, the electrolyzer, and the fuel cell. Other components such as hydrogen compressor and storage tanks exhibit negligible exergy destruction. The rate of exergy destroyed by the PV modules is determined as:

$$\dot{E}x_{des,PV} = \dot{E}x_{in,PV} + \dot{E}x_{th} - \dot{E}x_w \quad (4)$$

The exergy destruction rate in the solar collector is obtained from:

$$\dot{E}x_{des,Col} = \dot{S}_g T_{am} \quad (5)$$

The entropy generation rate of the solar collector, denoted as \dot{S}_g , is calculated as:

$$\dot{S}_g = \dot{m}c_p \ln \frac{T_{out}}{T_{in}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{so}}{T_{so}} + \frac{\dot{Q}_{lo}}{T_{am}} \quad (6)$$

The exergy destruction rate within electrolyzer is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}x_{des,EL} = & \left[\dot{Q}_{EL} \left(1 - \frac{T_{am}}{T_{EL}} \right) \right] + \dot{W}_{EL} + [\dot{E}x_{ph,H_2O} + \dot{E}x_{ch,H_2O}] - [\dot{E}x_{ph,O_2} + \dot{E}x_{ch,O_2}] \\ & - [\dot{E}x_{ph,H_2} + \dot{E}x_{ch,H_2}] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The exergy destruction rate in fuel cell can be obtained from:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}x_{des,FC} = & \left[\dot{Q}_{FC} \left(1 - \frac{T_{am}}{T_{FC}} \right) \right] + [\dot{E}x_{ph,O_2} + \dot{E}x_{ch,O_2}] + [\dot{E}x_{ph,H_2} + \dot{E}x_{ch,H_2}] - \dot{W}_{FC} \\ & - [\dot{E}x_{ph,H_2O} + \dot{E}x_{ch,H_2O}] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The total exergy destruction rate within the system is determined by aggregating the exergy destruction rates across all components of the system:

$$\dot{E}x_{des,sys} = \dot{E}x_{des,PV} + \dot{E}x_{des,Col} + \dot{E}x_{des,FC} + \dot{E}x_{des,EL} \quad (9)$$

This comprehensive calculation provides an accurate measure for the system's overall exergetic performance and identifies areas where improvements can be made. The proposed system must also be able to achieve a minimum LPSP as defined in Equation 10 [21].

$$LPSP = \sum_{t=1}^{t=8760} \frac{P_l - P_{PV} - P_{Col} - P_{FC}}{P_l} \quad (10)$$

SYSTEM MODELING

The entire system shown in Figure 1 was dynamically modeled using the TRNSYS software with 1-hour long time steps and components tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. TRNSYS modeling components

System Component	TRNSYS Component
Weather Data Processor	Type 15
Solar Thermal Collector	Type 1b
DHW Tank Storage	Type 4
Pump	Type 114
Water Profile	Type 14b
Differential Controller	Type 165
PV Array	Type 103
Effective Sky Temperature	Type 69
Alkaline Electrolyzer	Type 160
Compressor	Type 167
Compressed Hydrogen Gas Storage	Type 164
PEM Fuel Cell	Type 170
Controller	Type 105
TRNOPT	Type 583

To determine the optimal system sizing, an optimization approach was implemented to minimize the total exergy destruction (Equation 9), dumped electrical energy and LPSP. This was achieved through the application of the PSO method. Equipment sizes including number of PV modules, electrolyzer rated power, fuel cell rated power, hydrogen storage tank volume, solar collector area and hot water storage tank volume were treated as the variables, while the intervals within which the system operates effectively were set as constraints. This approach ensures that the system's performance is evaluated under feasible operating conditions. The values of the parameters used in the PSO method are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. PSO parameters

Parameter	Value
Population Size	25
Inertia Weight	0.95
Inertia Weight Damping Ratio	0.9
Personal Learning Coefficient	2.01
Global Learning Coefficient	1.92
Total Number of Iterations	50

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optimal system consists of a 7.2 kW_p PV array, a 6.7-kW electrolyzer, a 2.2-kW fuel cell, a 7-m³ hydrogen storage tank, a 10-m² solar thermal collector and a 0.35-m³ water storage tank. This configuration leads to zero values for both LPSP and electricity dump, indicating that the proposed system effectively uses all the excess electrical power and fully supplies the entire energy demand (30.54 MWh). The total annual exergy destruction for this configuration was found to be approximately 59 MWh.

Figure 2 shows the contribution of each component to the total exergy destruction. The PV array is the primary source of exergy destruction due to its relatively low conversion efficiency. The solar thermal collector and the alkaline electrolyzer are the next significant contributors, followed by the fuel cell. The less favorable exergetic performance of the PV array is also observed from Figure 3. A higher number of PV modules results in more occupied space and greater exergy destruction. The relationship between the total exergy destruction and the active PV area is almost linear, showing an upward trend. On the other hand, while an increase in collector area also raises the exergy destruction, its

effect is more gradual and less significant. Consequently, it can be deduced that the PV technology is generally less efficient than solar thermal systems.

Figure 2. Share of each system component in the total exergy destruction

Figure 3. The effect of PV and solar collector active area on total exergy destruction

The proposed HRES uses a controller that adjusts the amount of power transferred to the electrolyzer and the building. If the system is not properly sized, there might be unused electrical energy not captured by the electrolyzer.

Figure 4 illustrates how an increase in electrolyzer rated power can lower the amount of electrical energy dumped by the controller. This quantity approaches zero when the installed capacity of water electrolysis reaches 6.7 kW in a

configuration with 18 PV modules. Figure 4 also shows that there is an exponential relationship between the electrolyzer power and the dumped electrical energy.

Figure 4- The effect of electrolyzer rated power on dumped electrical energy

CONCLUSION

A stand-alone HRES incorporating solar PV and solar thermal energy through a PV array and a flat plate collector along with hydrogen energy storage was proposed and optimally sized using the PSO method in the TRNSYS software. The optimized system can deliver 30.54 MWh of energy with no LPSP, zero electricity dump and a minimum exergy destruction of 59 MWh. This is achieved by installing a 7.2 kWp PV array, a 6.7-kW electrolyzer, a 2.2-kW fuel cell, and 10-m² of solar thermal collector.

The system's exergetic performance is primarily influenced by the number of installed PV modules, as an increase in the PV array's occupied space leads to a linear rise in total exergy destruction. At a constant PV nominal power, the electrolyzer is the main contributor to electrical power dumped by the controller. Increasing the electrolyzer power exponentially reduces the electricity dump.

Overall, 73% of the total exergy destruction is due to the PV array, while the solar thermal collector and electrolyzer each account for 10%, and the fuel cell contributes only 7%. On the whole, a well-balanced system design can effectively meet energy demands while enhancing sustainability.

NOMENCLATURE

A	Area, m^2
C_p	Specific heat, $kJ / kg \text{ } ^\circ C$
$\dot{E}x$	Exergy Rate, W
G	Global Radiation, W/m^2
\dot{m}	Mass flowrate, kg/s
n	Number of PV modules
P	Power
\dot{Q}	Heat transfer rate, W
\dot{S}_g	Entropy generation rate, $J/^\circ C$
T	Temperature, $^\circ C$
t	Time
\dot{W}	Power rate, W

Greek symbols

α	Absorptivity coefficient
τ	Reflectivity coefficient

Subscripts

<i>am</i>	Refers to ambient
<i>ch</i>	Refers to chemical
<i>col</i>	Refers to collector
<i>des</i>	Refers to destroyed
<i>EL</i>	Refers to electrolyzer
<i>FC</i>	Refers to fuel cell
<i>g</i>	Refers to generation
<i>H₂O</i>	Refers to water vapor
<i>in</i>	Refers to input
<i>l</i>	Refers to load
<i>lo</i>	Refers to loss
<i>out</i>	Refers to output
<i>O₂</i>	Refers to oxygen gas
<i>PV</i>	Refers to photovoltaic
<i>ph</i>	Refers to physical
<i>so</i>	Refers to solar
<i>sys</i>	Refers to system
<i>th</i>	Refers to thermal
<i>w</i>	Refers to work

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